
Effects of Multimedia and Problem-Based Learning Strategies on Students' Listening Skills, Academic Achievement and Retention in Mathematics in Akwa Ibom State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of Multimedia Learning Strategy (MLS/CAL) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) on students' listening skills, academic achievement, and retention in Mathematics in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study adopted a non-equivalent quasi-experimental design involving three groups: two experimental groups and one control group. A multistage sampling technique was used to select 155 Senior Secondary School One (SS1) students (61 males and 94 females) from public co-educational secondary schools in Uyo. Experimental Group I was taught using Computer-Aided Learning (CAL/Multimedia), Experimental Group II was taught using Problem-Based Learning (PBL), while the Control Group was taught using the Conventional (lecture) method. Data were collected using the Statistics Achievement Test (SAT) and the Mathematics Language Skills Scale (MLSS), both of which were validated by experts and found to be reliable at a Kuder-Richardson coefficient of 0.90. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the three null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that students taught using PBL achieved the highest mean gain score compared to CAL and the Conventional method, and that this difference was statistically significant. With regard to retention, PBL students similarly recorded the highest mean retention score compared to CAL and Conventional groups, with the difference also found to be statistically significant. On the influence of gender, female students recorded slightly higher mean achievement scores than their male counterparts across all three instructional strategies; however, this difference was not statistically significant, indicating that the instructional strategies benefited both male and female students equitably. The study concluded that PBL and CAL are significantly more effective than conventional teaching in enhancing students' achievement and retention in Mathematics, with PBL emerging as the most effective strategy. It was recommended that Mathematics teachers adopt PBL as a primary instructional strategy, that secondary school teachers be encouraged to develop computer literacy for effective use of CAL packages, and that curriculum developers incorporate PBL and CAL into the Nigerian Mathematics curriculum.

KEYWORDS: Multimedia Learning Strategy, Computer-Aided Learning, Problem-Based Learning, Academic Achievement, Retention, Listening Skills, Mathematics, Gender, Akwa Ibom State.

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INTRODUCTION

Mathematics teaching and learning process has gradually the main focus of global discourse. Societal and educational value placed on Mathematics as a subject has made it becomes imperative that when academic ought to be proven as outstanding, it starts with one's ability to understand and carry out simple computational problem (Zechariah, 2012).

Since Nigeria obtained her independence in 1960, mathematics education has continue to receive special emphasis and attention. This is perhaps, in recognition of the contribution of Mathematics to the overall development of a nation which cannot be underestimated in view of its role for social and economic development. Thus, the quest for national development along with

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scientific, technological growth and self-reliance are matched with corresponding progress in Mathematics (Kuaru, 2016). Adeleke (2007) indicated that in the twenty first century, developing nations have come to realize that the increasing role of science and technology with strong Mathematics content is suitable instrument for National Development. Some of these roles include its ability to enable, and rational rethinking capabilities of individuals by making one to be creative, reasonable, and rational as well as imaginative. Akuka (2012) positioned that Mathematics has been recognized as a tool for solving everyday problem faced by individuals and the society. Even the most ordinary citizen has to calculate his wages and buy things from the market. For a housewife, farmer, trader, laborers, shopkeeper or accountant, some knowledge of Mathematics is necessary to carry out one's job. In the same vein, Agwagah (2013) indicate that Mathematics is an indispensable tool in virtually all human endeavors and there is hardly any field where Mathematics is not useful. That is why Mathematics has been placed as a compulsory subject both at primary and secondary school levels in Nigeria.

Despite the importance of Mathematics, many problems seem to beset its teaching in Nigeria. This has resulted to the consistent poor performance in Senior School certificate Examination (SSCE) in the subject (Abakpa, 2014). Prominent among these challenges, according to (Esuong, Udo and Item 2024) are; lack of qualified professional Mathematics teachers; non-use of appropriate instructional strategy; large class size; limited programmes for updating teachers' knowledge overcrowded classrooms; students' negative attitude toward Mathematics, inadequate facilities and Mathematics laboratories in our schools to mention but a few. This catalogue of challenges does not create conducive environment for Mathematics education to thrive in this country. It is on this note, Onah, Ugwuanyi, Okeke. Nworgu, Agwagah, Ugwuany, Obe, Nwoye and Okeke (2020) suggested that since students are very much interested and excited in the use of computer system, it is necessary for mathematics teachers to use the opportunity and apply machine, as teaching aid. Explaining further, they further asserted that computer is highly adaptable in teaching vital parts of Mathematics, most especially the elementary parts.

It enables the students to grasp the major background concepts behind advanced Mathematics calculations (Edoho & Esuong, 2016). Thus, the use computer in teaching multimedia projection package strategy and e-learning can be referred to as any computer-mediated software or interactive application that integrates text, colour, graphical images animation, audio sound, and full motion video in a single application. Multimedia learning systems consist of animation and narration which offer a potential avenue for improving students' understanding (Moreno & Mayer, 2010) Also, problem-Based Learning (PBL) is a classroom strategy that organizes Mathematics instructional around problem solving activities and affords students more opportunities to think critically, present their own creative ideas and communicate with peers Mathematically.

However, Listening Skill is one of the major problems affecting acquisition new knowledge during teaching and learning process. Good ability in listening meaning competency to comprehend information during listening activities or transfer the information in written or oral communication. It relates to the ability of understanding communication and responding what is listened (Hadyah, & Shalawatu, 2016).

Therefore, the researcher is of the probable opinion that multimedia and problem-based learning strategies are used it will increase students' achievement, retention and listening skill Mathematics.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Every year WAEC report low students' achievement in Mathematics. The council attribute this to lack of conceptual understanding among the students. Many reasons can be postulated to explained why students lack conceptual understanding. Some researchers have identified the use of teacher-centered approaches in teaching Mathematics, high teacher-students ratio, teachers' absenteeism, among other factors (Esuong, 2016; Ofonime, 2016; Ekwueme, 2013; Edoho, 2018).

Several interventions have been put into place address this low students' achievement in Mathematics in WAEC and other examinations. These issues of inadequate resources have been addressed through the education trust funds and intervention program organize for Mathematics and science teacher yearly. However, the student's low achievement in Mathematics persists. This implies that there could be other instructional issues responsible for the low students' achievement in Mathematics. Some methods used in teaching Mathematics do not seem to help in improving students' academic achievement. It is therefore inevitable to bring out other instructional strategies that could enhance effective teaching and learning of Mathematics. The problem this study seeks to solve is to investigate the effectiveness of MLS (CAL) and problem-based learning in enhancing students listening skills" academic achievement and retention in Mathematics? The study attempt to find answers to these questions.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of multimedia (CAL) and problem-based learning strategies on students' listening skills academic achievement and retention in senior secondary one (1) Mathematics students. Especially, the study will seek to:

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- i) Determine the effect of multimedia, PBL and conventional teaching strategies on students' listening skills on academic achievement in Mathematics.
- ii) Determine the effects of multimedia, PBL and conventional teaching strategies on students' retention in Mathematics.
- iii) Assess the influence of gender on students achievement in mathematics using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The following research questions are formulated to achieve the stated objectives:

1. What are the Mean Achievement Scores of Students in Mathematics when taught using multimedia CAL, PBL and Conventional Teaching Strategies?
2. What are the Mean Retention Scores of Students in Mathematics when taught using multimedia CAL, PBL and Conventional Teaching Strategies?
3. What are the Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students in Mathematics when taught using multimedia CAL, PBL and Conventional Teaching Strategies?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses (H_0) were tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study.

- H₀₁:** There are no significant differences among the academic achievement of students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies.
- H₀₂:** There are no significant differences among students in the retention of mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant difference between the achievement of male and female students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature relating to effect of multimedia and problem-based learning strategies on students' listening skills, academic achievement and retention in Mathematics in Uo, Akwa Ibom state is discussed under the following subheadings;

Strategies for Teaching and Learning of Mathematics

These researchers Eze (2011) and Ifeanacho (2012) believe that ineffective teaching strategies adopted in the teaching of Mathematics, often lead students' poor achievement and retention. They have experiment various methods for the improvement of teaching and learning of Mathematics. However, the achievement of students still remains poor. These teaching strategies aim at securing the advantages of individualized instruction retaining, making the learning very easy, and arousing students' interest socially. The alarming poor state of mathematics education in our schools are revealed by the students' dismal performance in public examination in public examination such as SSCE and JAMB, calls for an urgent need to constantly seek ways of improving the teaching and learning of the subject. Such efforts could be geared towards evolving new strategies and total transformation of the mathematics education programmes. For the benefit of this research work, three strategies out of many conceptualized have been put forward for consideration. They are; multimedia learning strategy, Problem Based learning and Conventional learning strategies.

Multimedia Learning Strategies

Multimedia is a new teaching and learning strategies in which the topic to be taught is carefully planned, written and programmed in a computer which could be run at the same time in several computer units (Eze, Ezenwafor and Onwasu, 2020). Moreno and Mayer (2010) defined multimedia to be any computer-mediated software or interactive application that integrates text, color, graphical images, animation, audio sound, and full motion video in a single application. Multimedia learning system consists of animation and narration which offers a potential venue for improving student understanding (Eze, Ezenwafor and Onwasu, 2020). Multimedia technologies are probably one of the most existing innovations in the information in the information age. The rapid growth of multimedia technologies over the past decades has brought fundamental changes to educational system. It will create suitable learning context which enables learners to control the learning environment. Multimedia is a multi-sensory that stimulates multiple senses of audience at a time. Its interactive enables teachers to control the flow of information (Iqbal and Khan, 2015) Multimedia teaching strategy affects both aspects of teaching and learning. Iqbah and Khan (2015) further reiterate that it does theses in three ways: how it presents information; how students interact both with the medium and through the medium with the teacher and other learners; and how knowledge is structured within multimedia.

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Problem-Based Learning

Problem-based learning (PBL) is a pedagogical approach or teaching method in which complex real world problems are used as the vehicle to promote students learning of Mathematics concepts formula and principles as opposed to direct presentation of facts and concepts. Duch (2001) opined that, in addition to course content, PBL can promote the development of critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, communication skills, provide opportunities for working in group, finding and evaluating research materials and life-long learning. Nilson (2010) list the following learning outcomes that are associated with PBL. A well-designed PBL project provides students with the opportunity to develop skills related to; working in team, making projects and holding leadership roles, working independently, critical thinking and analysis, example concepts self-directed learning. Applying course content to real-world examples, researching information literacy problem solving across discipline.

Supporting this, Chinweoke (2016) report that PBL can be inform of discovery approach of learning where the learner is guided by the teacher to discover Mathematical facts and formulas through observations and organized activities. Chinweoke further iterated that, in this approach the teacher provides the necessary teaching materials and guides the students to carry out some activities which would lead the students to arrive at a new knowledge. Teachers should move from the "telling method" And select strategies that can promote active learning in the classroom as students understand Mathematics concepts and have higher retention when they actively participate in the lesson.

Conventional Method of Teaching

Conventional instruction method, otherwise known as traditional teaching method, refers to all the old-time teaching methods adopted before the advent of the modern scientific teaching methods (Ibritam, 2012). Azuka (2014) refers to it as the traditional method, lecture method, talk and chalk method or teacher centered method. He further stated that in this method, the teacher does a major part of the activities, and the students listen, and copy notes with little or no exercise. Though this method is costly, a bit faster and be used for large number students in a single period, it has been proven to be counterproductive as it does not ensure effective learning of Mathematics concepts.

Conventional teaching methods make students interested in class, discouraged, bored and reluctant to accomplish tasks given and perform poorly I test (Eze, & Aja, 2014). Conventional method of teaching will be used in this research to refers to teaching using chalk, board and lesson note for teachers, pen, paper and textbook for students. The control groups will be taught using this method of teaching and the outcomes (that is pre-test and post-test) on students' achievement, interest and retention on statistics achievement test (SAT) and Statistics Interest Scale (SIS) will be used in the analysis.

Achievement of Students in Mathematics

According to Azuka (2014) "achievement" means a thing that somebody has done successfully especially using ones' own effort and skill" Academic achievement has become an index of a child's future in this competitive world (Illiyas and Charles) Academic achievement has been one of the most important goals of the educational process. Achievement encompasses students' ability and performance. Academic achievement is highly needed in order to eradicate the record on poor performance of students in Mathematics (Onah, 2014).

Achievement is an outstanding change in students' behavior as a result of their exposure to a specific programmed instruction (Orobosa, 2016). In 2012, the percentage of students with 5 credits and above in Mathematics who in Mathematics who passes WAEC was 48.88%. In 2013, the result declined to 36.5% while in 2014, there was a mass failure as only 31.28% candidates obtained five credits in Mathematics and English. In 2015, it increased to 38.68%. in 2015, 52.97%; 59.22; in 2018 it declined to 50% and in 2019 64% (WAEC Chief Examiner's Report, 2016 – 2019). These percentage are still low as educators in the field of Mathematics Science are still worried on how to demystify this problem and increase academic achievement. The traditional telling method lecture method and teacher centeredness have seemingly not yielded the expected positive result. On that note, the need for a paradigm shift from teacher centeredness to student's centeredness, from lecture method to guided discovery and from passive techniques to actives learning techniques is highly needed (Oluwaniyi, 2010). The researcher believes that employing MLS-CAL as a teaching strategy, PBL and academic achievement may be increased to a reasonable percentage.

Summary of Reviewed Literature

Literature review will be done under three broad heading; conceptual, theoretical framework and empirical studies. Under the conceptual framework, concept of multimedia learning strategy, PBL, Conventional Method of Learning, Strategies for teaching and learning Mathematics, and listening skills in Mathematics, were reviewed. Under theoretical framework, two theories were viewed as they relate to the study. These include Thorndike decay theory of learning and Bruner theory and its application in teaching and learning of Mathematics were discussed. Empirical studies of previous scholarly works were also discussed in detail. The review also revealed that the following factors interplay resulting in the poor performance of learning in Mathematics tasks: negative attitudes of students toward Mathematics teachers negatives attitudes of students' peers, nature of Mathematics, cultural bearing of content =, poor students' background, lack of Mathematics laboratory, negative attitudes of parents and inappropriate

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strategy of teaching Mathematics. Researchers also suggested ways and strategies for arousing the interest of students in Mathematics. Some of the suggested ways include effective use of instructional materials, motivating the students, use of mathematical games, use of activity-based learning approach, provision of Mathematics workshop laboratory, relating Mathematics to other disciplines and improvement of the sound standing of teachers.

From literature reviewed, it has been discovered that multimedia technologies are probably one of the most existing innovations in the information age. The rapid growth has brought one fundamental changes to educational system and many parts of the world linked with these technologies in teaching and learning of Mathematics. For example, Computer Assisted Learning (CAI) packages are design to teach mathematics; they exhibit attractive features of interactivity graphics and sound, though it is at infant stage in Nigeria. In particular, not many experimental studies have been carried out o effect of multimedia projection strategy design inform of CAL on teaching Mathematics in Nigeria. Literature also reviews that problem based learning which is a students' centered pedagogy in which students learn about the subjects through experience of solving and open-ended problem found in trigger material, the process does not focus on problem solving with edifying solution but it permit for development of other desirable skills and attribute. This gap in knowledge which conventional strategy of teaching created is revealed in the literature review needs to be filled. This directed the focus of this studies.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design that adopted for this study is a non-equivalent quasi-experimental design with two level of instructional strategies (multimedia and problem-based learning strategies) three dependent variables (listening skill achievement and retention) and two independent variables (multimedia and problem based learning strategies). The design is chosen to ensure the separate examination of the main and interaction effect of instructional strategies, dependent variables and gender on students' achievement and retention in concept of Mathematics since intact group of participants shall be used in the experiment than assigning participant random to experiments treatments.

Study Area

The area of study is Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The latitudes of Uyo is 5.038963 and longitude is 7.909470. Uyo Nigeria is located at Nigeria country in the towns place category with the gps coordinates of 5° 2'20 .2668''7° 54'34.0920'' E. The current metro population in 2023 is 1,329,000. There are 14 public secondary school in Uyo Local Government Area.

The choice of Uyo in Akwa Ibom State is based on the fact; it is one of the states Nigeria where poor performance of students in mathematics has been reported WAEC Chief Examiner and Akwa Ibom State is ranked 17 out of 36 states in Nigeria in terms of academic performances in mathematics in Nigeria (WAEC Chief Examiner 2022).

Population of the study

The population of this study comprised all 61,889 Senior Secondary School one (SS1) students in Akwa Ibom State for the 2024/2025 academic session. The choice of Akwa Ibom State was based on the fact that it is one of the state in Nigeria where poor performance of students in mathematic has been reported by Chief WAEC examiner and is ranked 17 out of 36 states (WAEC Chief Examiner's Report, 2018). The choice of SS1 students was because statistics is found in SS1 curriculum. It is an appropriate level to test the strategies outlined in this study.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The multistage sampling technique was used to select the sample of 150 students (60 males and 90 females) samples used for this study.

Instrument for data collection

The following instruments was used to collect data for the study:

Statistics achievement test (SAT): pretest and posttest and mathematics language skills scale (MLSS).

Validation of the instrument

The researcher made draft of the SAT which contained 50 items together with the making guide was given to three independent assessors whose two will be lecturers in the Department of Science Education (Mathematics Unit), and one from Test and Evaluation unit in Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, for face ant content validation. They were requested to assess and comment on the workings of the items appropriateness and adequacy of the items in addressing the purposes and problems of the study, grammatical accuracy and relevance of the items. Their initial appraisal and comments may lead to elimination of poor items and increasing the number of items in the draft.

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Reliability of the study

To measure the internal consistency of the instrument, the 50 multiple choice test items was administered to 20 samples of Mathematics students who were not part of the main study but found to be equivalent in all aspects to the sample of the study. The results obtained in the administration was subjected Kuder-Richardson's Formular 20. And the internal consistency of 0.90 was obtained making the instrument reliable for the study.

Procedures for data collection

The researcher constructed Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) comprising 50 multiple choice items with option A-D and only one correct answer and mathematics language skills scales (MLSS). The test is used to determine the performance of students in mathematics when taught with two different instructional strategies.

To carry out the study, a letter of authorization has been submitted to enable the researcher gain access to the schools for admission of the instruments. Permission obtained from principal of the Sample Public Coeducational Secondary School in Uyo. Before the administration , all the copies the instruments will be assigned serial numbers so that it will ease sorting, classification, coding and avoid the problem of misallocation.

Treatment

There were three groups of students the experiments; the experimental group one, experimental group two and control group. Experimental group one received treatment on multimedia (CAL) while experimental group two received treatment on problem-based learning strategy and the control group received no treatment but taught by regular class teacher using prepared lesson plan who will act as research assistant. The instrument MLSS a 4-point scale bearing agreed (SA) (4 – point), Agreed(A) (3-Point), Disagreed (D) (2-Pint) and strongly Disagreed (1-Point) was distributed to the participant students. At the end of the experiments, the pretest administered to the students was recorded as raw scores and used for data analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

The research questions is analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) will be adopted to test of each of the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the mean achievement scores of students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies?

Mean and Standard deviation of students taught mathematics using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

Variable	Pre-test			Post-test		Achievement mean gain	
	Teaching strategies	N	X	SD	X		SD
CAL		52	42.43	10.28	56.42	12.40	13.99
PBL		53	42.12	9.90	56.81	11.94	14.69
LECTURE		50	41.46	10.02	45.32	10.35	3.86

Where N=Number of students, X=mean, SD = Standard deviation

The descriptive result section of table revealed that there is a difference in the mean achievement scores amongst students taught with CAL (13.99), PBL (14.69) and Conventional teaching strategy (3.86). This indicates that students taught mathematics using the Problem-based learning had the highest achievement mean gain which implies that students achieve better when taught using PBL.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference among the academic achievement scores of students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies.

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Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of students mean achievement scores when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	18288.825 ^a	6	3048.137	70.070	.000
Intercept	965.353	1	965.353	22.191	.000
PRETEST	13218.967	1	13218.967	303.876	.000
Group	1625.158	2	812.579	18.679	.000
GENDER	3.557	1	3.557	.082	.775
group * GENDER	220.581	2	110.290	2.535	.083
Error	6438.169	148	43.501		
Total	460016.000	155			
Corrected Total	24726.994	154			

a. R Squared = .740 (Adjusted R Squared = .729)

The result in table above revealed $F(2, 155) = 18.679, P > .05$. This shows that F-ratio of 18.68 for groups with P-value of 0.000 which is less than the significant value of .05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is therefore rejected which indicates that there is a significant difference between the academic achievement of students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

Research Question 2

What are the mean retention scores of students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies?

Mean and Standard deviation of retention scores of students taught mathematics using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

Variable Teaching strategies	Post-test			Retention		
	N	X	SD	X	SD	mean difference
CAL	52	56.42	12.40	62.29	13.03	5.87
PBL	53	56.81	11.94	63.19	12.44	6.38
LECTURE	50	45.32	10.35	46.28	10.95	0.96

Where N=Number of students, X=mean, SD = Standard deviation

The descriptive result section of table above reveals that there is a difference in the mean retention scores among students taught using CAL (62.29), PBL (63.19) and Conventional strategy (46.28). This indicates that students taught mathematics using the Problem-based learning had the highest mean difference of 6.38 over CAL (5.87) and CON (0.96) which implies that students retain better when taught using PBL.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference among students' scores in the retention of mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies.

Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of students mean retention scores when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	24439.060 ^a	3	8146.353	167.384	.000
Intercept	925.670	1	925.670	19.020	.000
POSTEST	15237.888	1	15237.888	313.094	.000

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Group	1246.612	2	623.306	12.807	.000
Error	7348.979	151	48.669		
Total	543050.000	155			
Corrected Total	31788.039	154			

a. R Squared = .769 (Adjusted R Squared = .764)

The result of Analysis of Covariance of table above reveals F (2,155=12.807, P> .05). This further showed the F-ratio of 12.807 for the groups with P-value of 0.00 which is less than the significant value of .05. Based on this result, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is therefore rejected which indicates that there exist a significant difference amongst the retention level of students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

Research Question 3

What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies?

Mean and standard Deviation of male and female students taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional strategies.

Source	MALE					FEMALE				
	N	Pretest		posttest		N	Pretest		posttest	
		X	SD	X	SD		X	SD	X	SD
CAL	21	42.43	10.28	54.65	11.78	32	47.88	10.56	57.53	12.83
PBL	20	42.11	9.90	52.67	11.15	32	46.68	8.92	59.63	11.50
CONTROL	20	40.90	9.19	45.05	10.67	30	42.50	10.56	45.50	10.31
Total	61					94				

Where N=Number of students, X=mean, SD = Standard deviation

The descriptive result section of table above revealed that there is a difference in the mean achievement scores of male students taught using CAL (54.65), PBL (52.67), Conventional strategy (45.05) and female students taught using CAL (57.53), PBL (59.63) and Conventional strategy (45.05). This indicates that female students had a higher mean than their male counterparts which implies that female students perform better than the male students when taught mathematics using the Problem-based learning.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference among the achievement of male and female students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and conventional teaching strategies.

Table 4.08 Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of male and female mean scores when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	18288.825 ^a	6	3048.137	70.070	.000
Intercept	965.353	1	965.353	22.191	.000
PRETEST	13218.967	1	13218.967	303.876	.000
Group	1625.158	2	812.579	18.679	.000
GENDER	3.557	1	3.557	.082	.775
group * GENDER	220.581	2	110.290	2.535	.083
Error	6438.169	148	43.501		
Total	460016.000	155			
Corrected Total	24726.994	154			

The result in table above showed F-ratio of .082 with P-value of .775 which is greater than the significant value of .05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is therefore not rejected which indicates that there is no significant difference between male and female students among the strategies with regards to students’ achievement in mathematics.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The following discussions were made based on the findings of this study.

Academic Achievement of students in Mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional strategies.

The result of the first hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference amongst the academic achievement of students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies. This result is not surprising since there was a significant difference in the post-test achievement scores of students in the experimental and control groups.

This implies that treatment offered to the experimental groups played a key role in improving students' knowledge of mathematical statistics. These findings support the finding of different researchers (Agwagah, 2005; Eze, 2011; Ifeanchi, 2012). These researchers believed that ineffective teaching strategies adopted in the teaching of mathematics, often leads to poor achievement and retention. They further opined that employing appropriate teaching strategies aimed at securing the advantages of individualized instruction retaining, making the learning very easy and arousing students' interest socially.

The result of the findings also supported Oluwaniyi (2010) who claimed that the conventional method and teacher's centeredness have seemingly not yielded the expected positive result. On the other note, the need for a paradigm shift from teacher centeredness to students' centeredness, from lecture method to guided discovery and from passive techniques to active learning techniques is highly needed. This claim corroborates with the researchers' view that employing MLS-CAL, PBL as teaching strategies, and academic achievement of students may be increased to reasonable percentage.

Retention of students in Mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

The result of the second hypothesis established that there is a significant difference amongst the retention level of students in mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies. This result is not surprising since there was a significant difference in the post-test retention mean on experimental and control groups. Results of the analysis insinuates that the treatments offered to the experimental groups played a key role in improving students' ability to retain what has been taught for a long time. This finding is not surprising because for a long term retention of materials in mathematical science, it is required that students practice active learning that involves critical thinking through discussion, individually or studying in groups.

This study supports the findings of Iwendi (2012) who posited that poor teaching method is one of the factors affecting successful outcome of students' retention. Hence, it is pertinent Mathematics concepts be presented to students in such strategies that will affect their sub-consciousness which can trigger quick recalling of the concepts being taught or learnt.

Achievement between male and female students in Mathematics when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

The result of the third hypothesis also revealed that female students slightly significantly differ from their male counterparts, in their academic achievement when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies.

This slightly significant difference of gender in academic achievement in mathematics is not surprising since there was slightly significant differences in the post-test mean academic achievement scores between the females who had a slightly higher mean difference than their male counterparts. However, the result of table 4.08 showed that this difference was not significant.

The result of this study agrees with the results of Ajai and Imoke (2015) who carried out studies to assess gender differences in mathematics achievement and retention using PBL. The study revealed that male and female students taught algebra using PBL did not significantly differ in achievement and retention scores; thereby revealing that male and female students are capable of competing and collaborating in mathematics. They said; achievement is a function of orientation, not gender.

On the contrary, Rodriguez, Regueiro, Estevez, Pineiro and Valle (2020) worked to verify gender differences, the study aimed to examine the explanatory potential of boys' and girls' attitudes towards mathematics on their performance in Spain. The results suggested that girls tender to exhibit less positive attitudes about mathematics than their male classmates. Particularly, lower motivation, worse perception of competence and higher rates of anxiety, although in all cases the effect sizes were small. Even though there is no significant gender difference in academic performance, as expected, the explanatory power of attitudes towards mathematics was clearly more significant in boys than in girls

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were made based on the findings of this study. The result of this study provides empirical evidence that the use of Problem-based learning (PBL) and Computer Aided learning strategies (CAL) enhanced students' achievement, retention and interest in mathematics more than the use of Conventional teaching strategies as Students taught mathematics using PBL strategy (Experimental group II) performed better than their counterpart taught using CAL (Experimental group I). While conventional method was third in achievement. The result of the Hypotheses showed that there exists significant difference among the strategies. Secondly, there exists a significant difference among the strategies with regards to students' retention in mathematics. Students

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taught using PBL retained more than those taught using CAL and the Conventional strategies. Therefore the use of PBL enhanced the teaching and learning of mathematics.

The test of hypothesis confirmed that there revealed that female students slightly significantly differ from their male counterparts, in their academic achievement when taught using CAL, PBL and Conventional teaching strategies. Therefore teachers should discourage on the use of conventional method of teaching mathematics but rather embrace teaching mathematics using PBL strategy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study.

1. Since the use of PBL strategy enhances achievement in Mathematics, mathematics teachers should use it as number one of its teaching strategies to be employed in classroom teaching and learning.
2. Secondary school teachers should be encouraged to be computer literate. This will enable them appreciate and use CAL packages to promote effective teaching and learning.
3. The Federal Government, State, Local Government, Organizations and Alumni Associations in Nigeria should endeavour, as a matter of dedication assist mathematics teachers to attend workshops/seminars organized in Nigeria and outside the Country.
4. Curriculum developers should embrace PBL and include Computer Aided Learning instructional strategies into Nigerian curriculum.

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